

The Impact of Solar Still Design on the Efficiency of Distillate Production: A Comprehensive Review

Felix Niyokwizera ✉

College of Environmental Science and Engineering,
Tongji University, 1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, China;
UNEP-Tongji Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development,
1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, China;
Department of Architecture and Design, University of Rwanda,
P.O. Box 3900, Kigali, Rwanda

Shamusideen Oseni

College of Environmental Science and Engineering,
Tongji University, 1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, China;
UNEP-Tongji Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development,
1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, China

Juvins Twizeyemungu

College of Environmental Science and Engineering,
Tongji University, 1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, China;
UNEP-Tongji Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development,
1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, China

Herman Nduwimana

College of Environmental Science and Engineering,
Tongji University, 1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, China;
UNEP-Tongji Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development,
1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, China

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ABSTRACT:

The global shortage of fresh water has grown exponentially due to population growth and the contamination of available water from human activities. Solar stills play an important role in providing clean water through solar-powered distillation. The efficiency of distillate generation is heavily influenced by design parameters, materials, and operating conditions. This comprehensive review investigates the effect of various solar still designs, such as conventional, stepped, multi-effect, and active solar stills, on water production efficiency. Key factors examined include basin area, water depth, cover inclination, thermal insulation, and integration with external energy sources. Modifications such as phase change materials (PCM), nanofluids, and reflectors significantly improve heat retention and evaporation rates, resulting in higher distillate yield. Comparative studies show that hybrid solar stills, which include photovoltaic panels or waste heat recovery systems, outperform traditional designs in terms of productivity. Furthermore, choosing the right materials for the basin and cover is critical for improving thermal conductivity and reducing heat loss. Improving energy absorption, reducing heat loss, and optimizing design configurations are critical for improving performance. The findings indicate that innovative design changes and

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innovative approaches can significantly increase freshwater production, making solar stills a viable solution for addressing water scarcity in arid and remote areas.

Keywords: Desalination, Solar still design, distillate, Productivity.

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INTRODUCTION

The access to clean water is the foundation of wellbeing of human life on the earth. Water is also considered as a gift from nature, but in nowadays many countries are facing water shortage challenges due to extremely population growth and the industrial sector and factories, which are causing more pollution of natural resources [1,2]. There are arid such as desert regions where regular rainfall is scarce and ground water scarcity; and even where there are many water bodies most of them are unsuitable for domestic irrigation, and particularly for drinking because they are brackish or saline in many parties of the countries like Middle Eastern and North African which are struggling because of lacking access to the clean water [3].

Normally the earth's surface is covered around 71% in water, the majority with 96.5% is found as saltwater in oceans. Only 2.5 percent of the world's water supply is comprised of freshwater, the most of which is either submerged in aquifers or frozen in glaciers and polar ice caps [4]. Less than 1% of freshwater, mostly found in rivers, lakes, and reservoirs, is still usable for human use [5-7].

There is an abundance of seawater with high salinity that requires salinity removal, which incurs additional energy costs for its treatment processes. Places with abundant solar radiation; brackish water could be used to supply reasonable amounts of potable water at low cost [8]. Solar remains a potential desalination technique since it is inexpensive, simple to install, and a manageable tool for supplying potable water to rural areas and remote areas [9]. Solar stills use a low-cost energy source, the sun, to provide a feasible alternative for water desalination that might be used for agriculture or even drinking.

For the purpose of solar distillation, it is intended to simulate the natural process of evaporation and condensation as it occurs. This technique eliminates contaminants like salts and heavy metals while also destroying microorganisms. The resulting water is cleaner than even the cleanest rainfall. Sun energy is more cost-effective than fossil fuels in isolated places with low population density, minimal rainfall, and ample sun energy. The production of fresh water by solar distillation is highly dependent on the strength of solar radiation, the number of sunlight hours, and the kind of still [10-12].

However, due to the low efficiency of daily production of yield from conventional solar still desalinations, the researchers have investigated different factors which can influence increasing distillate production from solar stills such as still design, operation condition and environmental influences.

This comprehensive review will explore different solar still design and their contribution to the production of distillate.

DESIGNS OF SOLAR STILL

A solar still is the apparatus used to perform solar distillation, began in the nineteenth century [13]. Solar stills have two main key features such as technical simplicity and the use of a free heat source like the sun. However, their productivity (a few $l/(m^2d)$) is relatively small, and over their operating history, many efforts have been made to improve their performance, even via relatively advanced designs [14].

There are two categories of solar stills: passive and active. The term passive still describes a type of still that specially uses solar energy that is converted into the still unit. These kinds of systems function similarly to nature's hydrological cycle. Evaporation and condensation processes take place

inside the still basin because it makes use of the heat that has built up in the saline water. However, in active solar stills, the still unit that helps heat the saline water should be powered by an external thermal energy source or device. Thermal collectors, photovoltaic panels, and sand concentrators coupled with the distillation unit could be used to generate this kind of energy. Such external heat, waste thermal energy, or a concentrating solar panel could be supplied by a traditional boiler [15,16].

Solar Still Design Parameters

A solar still's design parameters play important roles in determining its efficiency and water output. There are key parameters affecting evaporation and condensation rates such as surface area of evaporation and basin water depth, Slope of the cover, Material and thickness of the cover, Insulation material and thickness and The temperature difference of water and glass cover. The evaluation of these parameters are critical for increasing freshwater production and maintaining the sustainability of solar desalination systems, particularly in water-scarce areas.

Surface area of evaporation and basin water depth

Solar still surface area and water depth are the important component influencing distillate production. This is because the evaporation rate of distilled water is roughly proportional to the surface area of water exposed to sun radiation and should evaporate. As a result, increasing the surface area of salt water in the distiller's basin increases the efficiency of producing distilled fresh water. The water depth in the basin is inversely related to distillation efficiency and clean water productivity [17,18].

It has been documented that the lowest level of water correlates to the best productivity under steady solar radiation, and that a dry patch is achieved. It has been discovered that the solar still's production decreased as the water depth increased. It has been investigated by Elango and Murugavel that the effect of water depth increase on both types of sun distillers, single- and double-basin solar stills, and discovered that both types of solar stills had reduced production [13,19].

The influence of water quantity in the basin on solar still production was tested using varied amounts of water (6 L, 8 L, 10 L, and 12 L). The experiment results reveal that the single slope solar still has a total cumulative distillate production of 2490 mL, 2390 mL, 2240 mL, and 2015 mL, respectively. However, it has been shown that when basin water quantity increases, distillate water production decreases [20,21].

Overall, the suggested water depth in the basin was between 1 and 5 cm in all of the cases studied. Although the opposite occurs at night and during the day, production improves with increasing water depth, since nocturnal productivity follows a reversal pattern. At night, the depth of the basin's water increases, as does its volumetric heat capacity. Thus, a low evaporation rate is achieved. The desalination process continues throughout the night as the heat energy received by the water is released. As a result, larger volumes of water absorb more energy [13].

Solar still cover's slope

In the design process of solar still, the slope of the cover has an impact on distillate productivity because it influences to the condensation and collection of water vapor. An optimal slope ensures that condensed water droplets efficiently trickle down into the collection trough, reducing re-evaporation and increasing water yield. If the slope is too steep, water droplets may slide too quickly, reducing effective condensation time, whereas a very shallow slope can cause droplet accumulation, blocking solar radiation and slowing evaporation rates. Feilizadeh and his team ~~have been~~ conducted a research on three different angles 20,30,45⁰ and they found that Because of the higher temperature difference at 30 degrees, productivity is higher compare to the other cover slope angles [22].

Cover material and thickness

The transmissivity of the cover and its thickness are significant factors that influence the still's productivity. The thermal conductivity of the cover affects the still yield. The yield of a still with 4 mm, 5 mm, and 6 mm glass was calculated to be 4.20 L, 3.97 L, and 3.86 L, respectively. As a result, a still with a 4 mm glass cover produced 14% more fresh water than an identical still with a 6 mm glass cover. This is because thinner glass has a higher transmittance, allowing more solar radiation to be admitted into the still and thus reach the basin water [19].

Dimri and his team examined the impact of different still cover materials, including glass, plastic, and copper, on maximum still productivity. According to their experimental findings, copper has the highest still productivity, while using plastic materials as a cover has the lowest productivity [23].

Insulation material and thickness

The designing of solar still is based on it is critical to choose the right insulation material and thickness to maximize distillate production. Effective insulation reduces heat loss from the basin, ensuring higher water temperatures and prolonged evaporation, the insulation material and thickness are important factors in solar stills [24-26]. The research conducted by [24] and his team shown that the monthly average daily production in June was 2.46 kg/m²/d for a non-insulated still and 2.84 kg/m²/d for an insulated still [24]. Solar stills with insulation thicknesses of 30, 60, and 100 mm are studied, and the results are compared to those obtained for a still without insulation. It was discovered that insulation thickness has a significant impact on the still's productivity up to 60 mm. The insulation thickness might affect the still's productivity by more than 80% [25].

The temperature difference of water and glass cover

The difference in temperature between the water in the basin and the glass cover is proportional to the solar still's productivity yield. The temperature difference serves as a significant driving force for the mechanism of a solar still. Al-Garni found that applying a cooling water film to the glass cover increased the still yield [27]. While Murugavel and his team found also that using an electric resistance heater to heat water increased the temperature difference between the basin and glass cover [28]. As a result, higher water temperatures increase evaporation while lower glass cover temperatures increase condensation. Therefore, it is possible to conclude that the greater the temperature difference between the water and the glass cover, the more solar distillate is collected.

Other parameters affecting the productivity of solar stills

Solar still is a device designed in order to produce clean water, as it is solar based device the increasing solar radiation intensity improves still desalination productivity [29]. Solar stills typically achieve their highest productivity around solar noon, when the intensity of solar radiation reaches its peak temperature. This facilitates and accelerates the rate of water evaporation. Furthermore, the intensity of solar radiation varies depending on the geographical location and time of year, which is determined by latitude, longitude and time. The intensity of solar radiation is predictable based on mathematical simulation models [30,31]. It has reported that the intensity of solar radiation in a city in northern Egypt varies throughout the day, with the highest solar intensity recorded around solar noon during the summer rather than the winter season [32]. solar radiation intensity has a significant impact on receiving surface temperature, affecting heating system processes like solar desalination [33]. The wind speed over the glass cover, as well as the intensity of the sun's radiation, have a significant impact on solar still efficiency. The temperature of the glass surface decreases due to convective heat transfer as the wind speed increases.

PASSIVE SOLAR STILL DESIGN

Passive solar stills are simple, energy-efficient devices that use solar energy to purify water via evaporation and condensation without intervention of external sources of energy or devices [34]. Their standard design includes a basin with saline or polluted water, a transparent cover to capture solar energy, and a slanted surface for collecting distilled water. Passive solar stills can be distinct with different aspect such as shape of cover, number of basins, shape of still and operation processes.

Single Slope Basin Solar Still

single slope basin solar still design is the primary type of solar still and is also considered as the conventional passive solar still [35]. Many researchers presented architectural designs that were optimized theoretical and experimental testing. Figure 1 shows the container is covered with a sloping glass cover that is well sealed to prevent vapour leakage. This container is supported by an appropriately insulated hardwood frame. The polluted water absorbs sun energy and hence gets

heated. Increasing the temperature of dirty water causes water molecules to evaporate. Convection happens in the air above the water's surface. The vapors then move into basin space and come into contact with the glass lid. Heat is then absorbed into the cover material, causing the vapors to condense as droplets on the tilt cover. The condensate droplets are collected in the distilling channel on the bottom wall of the still basin, leaving all salts and pollutants in the tank to be emptied later by drainage [17,32]. A conventional solar still converts saltwater and brackish water into potable water. Due to its low productivity, it is rarely used [36]. The single solar stills typically achieve a maximum efficiency of 50% with complete insulation. Less insulation reduces efficiency by around 14.5%. Increasing wind velocity from 0 to 1.6 m/s results in a minor 2% decrease in still performance [37].

Figure 1. A Schematic Diagram of a Simple Solar Still
Source: [37]

Double Slope Solar Still

A double-slope solar still is a passive solar device used to desalinate or purify water by absorbing sun energy. It consists of a basin filled with saline or polluted water, which is covered by a transparent, sloping roof with two glass or plastic slopes. The gadget operates on the concept of evaporation and condensation. Solar radiation warms the water in the basin, which evaporates. The vapour rises and condenses on the sloping roof's inner surface, which is colder owing to contact with the surrounding air. The condensed water droplets glide down the sloping surface and accumulate in separate channels on each side, resulting in fresh, distilled water. Double-slope solar stills are very useful in places with high solar intensity since the two slopes maximise the surface area exposed to sunlight, increasing efficiency [38]. The operational parameters are feed water volume, water depth, and direction. The impact of operating parameters on internal heat and mass transfer, and therefore on the productivity of a double slope (DS) solar still, was examined and compared to that of a single slope (SS) solar still. Both SS and DS solar stills of identical dimensions are constructed, and experiments are performed by keeping the water depth in the basin at 0.01m, 0.025m, 0.05m, and 0.075m after establishing the orientation. The peak distillate yield of 3.07L/m²/day was achieved at a water depth of 0.01m in the DS solar still orientated north-south [39]. They are easy to build, inexpensive, and ecologically beneficial, with no upkeep and no external energy source.

Figure 2. Schematic Arrangement of a Double Slope Solar Still
Source: [40]

A Double-Effect Solar Still

The design process of a double-effect solar still can be also called double basin solar still involves careful planning to optimize water production efficiency while utilizing solar energy effectively. It starts with identifying the objectives, such as desired water output, cost constraints, and environmental conditions like solar intensity and ambient temperature. Figure 3 shows the system layout is then conceptualized, typically featuring two stages of evaporation and condensation. Transparent covers, often made of glass or high-quality plastic, are designed to maximize solar heat absorption. The basin is engineered with an appropriate material for thermal conductivity and insulation to retain heat efficiently. The first stage includes a saline water basin that captures solar energy to evaporate water, while the second stage is designed to harness the latent heat released during condensation in the first stage to initiate another evaporation cycle. A double effect solar still uses sloped glass to separate the upper and lower basins, with heat transfer occurring through evaporation and radiation. This method produces more distilled water than a single effect type [41].

Figure 3. Double Effect Basin Still
Source: (Fath, 2010)

The two basins are sealed to prevent water from leaking into the boxes and stills; the condensed water collection and brackish water feeding occur through the sidewall hole of the basin, which is closed with insulating material while still preventing heat and vapour losses [42], condensation

surfaces are positioned and angled to collect distilled water; heat recovery mechanisms, such as thin-film heat exchangers, are incorporated to transfer heat between stages; insulation is added to minimize heat loss; and water channels are designed for effective flow and separation of freshwater from brine. The simulation ran for eight hours, and the results were compared to the experiment; the experimental results showed a total distilled output of 3.2 L/m² channel; however, the analytical results yielded 3.74 L/m² collected in output; the simulation results followed the same trend as the real data and were in excellent agreement with each other [43].

Simple Stepped Cascade Stills

Simple stepped cascade stills are intended to improve the efficiency of conventional solar stills by using multiple inclined steps to increase water evaporation and condensation. The design is made up of a series of shallow, inclined trays or steps that allow thin layers of saline or contaminated water to flow downward while exposed to solar radiation. A transparent cover, typically made of glass or plastic, traps solar energy and creates a greenhouse effect, which heats the water. As the water evaporates, the vapour condenses on the cover's underside and collects in a separate channel as distilled water.

As it shows on the Figure 4, the logic behind this design is to maximise the area of water exposed to solar radiation while minimizing thermal losses. Unlike conventional basin-type solar stills, which have a relatively high water depth, distance from saline water to the glass cover of still, stepped cascade stills use thin water films, which heat up and evaporate faster. The cascading movement exposes fresh water to solar heat on a continuous basis, increasing overall evaporation rates. In addition, the design reduces thermal inertia, allowing the system to respond more efficiently to variations in solar intensity. The steps also generate a convective air current within the still, which enhances heat and mass transfer.

Stepped solar stills can be used either passively or actively. However, passive stepped stills have many advantages in terms of cost efficiency because no electrical pumping power is required, in addition to their simplicity of design and operation. However, its low efficiency, as measured by low freshwater production, remains an obstacle when compared to active stepped solar. This disadvantage is caused by the loss of latent heat from condensation through the transparent cover [44].

Figure 4. Simple Stepped Basin Solar Still
Source: [44]

Furthermore, the step tray width and depth sizes had a significant impact on the stepped still's daily efficiency. Experimental results showed that with a tray width of 120 mm and a depth of 5 mm, the stepped still's maximum daily productivity was approximately 57.3% higher than that of the conventional one. Furthermore, the daily efficiency of both stepped and conventional stills were approximately 53% and 33.5%, respectively. The wicks increased the stepped still's productivity by up to 5% while feed seawater preheating reduced modified system efficiency by half and increased productivity slightly. However, their maximum obtained daily productivity was 6.080 l/m² /day at an efficiency of 66.6%, whereas the calculated maximum theoretical productivity of their system was 9.129 l/m²/day [45].

Pyramid Solar Still

A pyramidal solar still is a still with a top cover shaped as a pyramid Figure 5. The basins of solar stills are available in two shapes triangular pyramids and square pyramids. The pyramid solar still has some advantages over the conventional basin solar still. For example, in a conventional solar still, the still must be tracked to face the sun throughout the day in order to receive the maximum incident solar radiation, whereas in a pyramidal glass solar still, this is not required [48]. The pyramid shape solar still has a much higher condensation rate than a conventional single slope solar still for the same basin area [46,47]. An experimental study conducted in southern Egypt at Aswan city comparing the pyramid-shaped solar still to the single slope solar still. The results of their work revealed that the still's annual average daily productivity is 2.6 L/m² day [46]. Such results indicated that the pyramid solar still configuration could be a viable alternative to the single slope solar still.

Also, it has been investigated a concave-shaped basin solar still with a pyramid-shaped top cover. The concave-shaped basin is supported by wick, which increases the still's daily productivity. Their findings revealed that during the day, an average distillate productivity of 4.1 L/m² could be collected. Their system efficiency was recorded at 45%, compared to 30% for the ordinary pyramid solar still, and the cost efficiency was 28% for the concave pyramid-shaped solar still, indicating that the structure is also financially valuable [49].

The conducted experiments on triangular solar stills and showed that water depth is a significant factor influencing still productivity and efficiency [50]. It was also discovered that the accumulated distillate water productivity from square pyramid solar stills decreases as the glass cover angle exceeds the latitude angle. The maximum accumulated distillate water productivity from square pyramid solar stills occurs when the glass cover angle matches the Latitude angle [51].

Figure 5. Pyramid solar stills with different angles of top glass cover
Source: [51]

Conical Hemispherical Solar Still

A hemispherical solar still consists of a transparent acrylic cover and a circular water basin. The salt water in the basin absorbs thermal solar heat, which is transmitted through the transparent acrylic cover. Thermal processes cause brine water to heat up and evaporate. Gravity causes the condensed water to flow down the sides of the cap, where it is collected [52]. The experimental conducted shown the results that the daily productivity for hemispherical conical stills is 3.38 L/m².day, while conventional basin solar stills were 1.93 L/m².day, under the same weather conditions [53].

Furthermore, Ismail stated that the use of a hemispherical solar still in his study yielded a distillate ranging from 2.8 to 5.7 L/m². day, with efficacy decreasing by 8% with a 50% increase in saline water depth in the still basin [54]. However, Arunkumar and his team investigated the parameters that affect the performance of the hemispherical conical still, and found that the temperature difference between water and glass has a significant effect on still productivity. Thus, they discovered that cooling water over the hemispherical cover increases the collected distillate; such criteria could be met by lowering air or water over the hemispherical cover, as the driving force of solar still is determined by the temperature difference between water and glass. This hemispherical still, as opposed to the traditional flat, could speed up the process by 1.25 times. The still's output when the cover is cooled and when it is not cooled are 4.2 and 3.5 kg/m² day, respectively [55].

Figure 6. Hemispherical Solar Distiller Design
Source: [52]

Wick-Type Solar Still

Solar radiation that falls on the glass cover is transmitted through it and absorbed at the wick surface. A portion of the energy is used to heat the water flowing through the wick due to capillary action. A large amount of heat is trapped inside the still, and energy is transferred from the wick surface to the glass cover and into the surrounding air. Heat transfers in the distillation system are controlled by both external and internal modes. The external heat transfer mode occurs outside the still and is caused by independent convection and radiation. The internal heat transfer mode of the solar distillation unit occurs as a result of radiation, convection, and evaporation. In the internal heat transfer mode, mass transfer is combined with radiative and convective heat transfer. Water flowing across the wick surface is heated and evaporated into vapours. Following the release of the latent

heat of vaporisation, the saturated water vapour condenses on the lower surface of the glass cover. Gravity causes condensed water droplets to trickle down and collect in the drainage channel [56].

A wicked solar still can also be identified by the type of inclined solar still. Wicks are substances that can absorb solar radiation, increasing the still's efficiency and productivity. Such materials are porous, allowing for radiation-absorbing pads [56,57]. Different experimental studies have shown that using wick materials increases still productivity, and tilting such substances can increase evaporation rates [58]. The floating tilted-wick type, the lowering water low rate inside the still via the tilted wick portion, and the absorption capacity of the wick material surface all contribute to still efficiency [56].

Wicked-type solar stills can be classified into several types, including multi-wick type stills, which achieve high productivity by combining various types of wicked materials, such as an evaporating wick, a condensing wick, and a polytetrafluoroethylene net sandwich. Furthermore, the wicked-type solar still can be converted to a concave-wick type solar still. This type is based on the evaporation rate of water, which increases as the water level in the basin decreases. According to the research, productivity may be increased to 4.1 L/m with a 30% efficiency [59].

Figure 7. Tilted wick type solar still
Source: [60]

Solar Still with External Reflectors

The design of a solar still with an external reflector is on using reflecting surfaces to optimize solar energy collection and system performance. Reflectors, either internal or external, are a good and inexpensive modification to increase the solar irradiation directed to the basin liner or the water as well as the distillate efficiency of the still [61]. Researcher has shown that the conventional still has limited productivity, so scientists have worked to create a variety of solar still designs to increase productivity and have concluded that solar stills integrated with reflectors are one of the most efficient and effective designs [61].

Numerical analysis was also performed utilizing heat and mass transport within the solar still and evaluated against experimental data. External reflectors were proven to considerably boost the productivity of the solar still, and an increase in the distillate of roughly 82% was recorded in this investigation [62].

The effects of reflector height and angle on solar input, water production rate, and gain output ratio (GOR) were investigated. The study found that using an ideal reflector configuration of 40 mm height and 120° angle resulted in a water production rate of 5.98 kg m⁻²hr⁻¹ and a GOR increase of 156%. Theoretical investigation looked at heat dispersion and thermal efficiency over different air gaps and solar radiation intensities. In the initial stage, evaporation was the primary heat source, attaining 91% thermal efficiency with a 6.5 mm air gap and 1.50 kW m⁻² of reflected solar energy. In contrast, a 16

mm gap drastically reduced efficiency to 72% in the last stage owing to increased lateral heat loss [63].

Solar Still with Condenser

In the condenser solar still, top and bottom losses in the solar still have a greater influence on production because of the bigger temperature differential between evaporation and condensation inside the solar still. Because of the increased temperature differential, vapour is formed within the solar still and is occasionally lost through the still's glass cover, reducing distillate production and productivity. To maximize production, maintain this temperature differential, which lowers heat loss. The addition of fans, reflectors, water sprinkling, and condensers reduces heat loss by maintaining a reduced temperature differential. The purging contribution is expressed as the fraction $[\text{condenser volume} / (\text{condenser volume} + \text{still volume})]$ of the still yield. Natural circulation accounts for about 75% of total still yield. An experimental research to imitate the purging mass transfer mechanism was conducted. The experimental findings indicate excellent agreement with theoretical expectations and a 50% improvement in still efficiency [64].

As shown in Figure 8, a condenser is used with the solar still to maintain the temperature difference and reduce heat losses. The vapors generated inside the still is moved with the help of the fan inside the condenser, where it can be condensed, and this condensed vapour can be converted to water and collected through the trough outside the condenser. This method allows for a larger distillate yield while decreasing heat loss [51,65]. Bhardwaj and his team conducted an experiment on the still's basin with the area of 1.8 m². The tests were carried out in a lab setting at varying water temperatures. The still produced 0.75 l of water per hour at a water temperature of 73 ° C. Furthermore, using air flow over the passive condenser to simulate wind or wet tissue to simulate evaporation cooling raised water production to more than 0.95 l/h [66].

Figure 8. Stepped Solar Still with Mirrors, Fan and Condenser
Source: [67]

Phase Change Materials

Latent heat storage occurs when a substance undergoes a phase transition in response to heat. For instance, a substance may transition from liquid to vapor by storing heat as latent heat of vaporization, or from solid to liquid via latent heat of fusion. According to Fath latent heat thermal energy storage systems provide advantages over sensible heat storage systems, such as consistent temperature for charging and discharging and high energy storage capacity per volume [68].

Radhwan conducted a research on the temporary performance of an immersed solar still with compact latent heat thermal energy storage for the purpose of warming and humidifying agricultural greenhouses. He also addressed how wax thickness and air flow rate affect system function.

Minimizing the air flow rate significantly increased the still production while reducing the greenhouse heat burden. The entire production is around 4.6 L/m² with an efficiency of roughly 57% [69].

The researchers investigated the effectiveness of various material types in increasing still productivity. They compared the productivity of various solar stills made of aluminum and galvanized iron, and the results revealed that both types produced 3.8 and 2.6 L/m² per day, respectively. This could be due to the different thermal conductivity of the materials, as aluminum has a higher thermal conductivity than galvanized iron stills [70].

Naim and Mona's research revealed that using an energy storage material increased the productivity of distilled water, while increasing the concentration of saline water decreased the productivity of the still. Higher flowrates and saline water temperatures at the input enhanced still efficiency. The greatest productivity of the still was 4.536 L/m² in 6 hours of daytime operation plus nocturnal distillation due to stored energy, when the saline water flowrate was 40 ml/min, resulting in a still efficiency of 36.2% [71].

Solar Still with Sponges and Gravels

Efficiency of water evaporation and condensation in solar still can be improved by including sponge cubes in the basin. The still comprises of a translucent cover allowing sunshine to penetrate through, enabling heating of the water. Arranged in the basin, sponge cubes absorb and retain more water, hence enhancing surface area for evaporation. Rising, condensing on the lid, the evaporating water drops into a collecting container. Especially in cases of fluctuating water levels, the sponges help to retain water, therefore guaranteeing a consistent supply of evaporating moisture. The sponge cubes into the basin water significantly increases still output (up to 273%). The sponge cubes enhance the surface area on which water evaporates [72].

The effectiveness of the solar still was analyzed with several spreader materials, including jute cloth, cotton cloth, a sponge sheet, and porous materials like quartzite rock and natural rock, researches confirmed that using a black light cotton cloth resulted in the highest output demonstrated the temporary performance of an active single basin solar still with a thin coating of a sensible storage material beneath the still's basin liner to create fresh water at night [73,74].

The addition of 10 kg sand as storage material increased daily production to around 4.005 (L/m²/day) with a daily efficiency of approximately 37.8%. Without sand, production decreased to 2.852 L/m²/day, resulting in a 27% efficiency. The yearly average daily output of the still with storage was found to be 23.8% higher than without storage [73]. Nafey and his team investigated the effect of black gravel on the solar still's production. The use of 20-30 mm black gravel with a brine volume of 20 L/m² and a glass cover angle of 15° increased productivities by 19% [75].

Figure 9. Over Three Days, Water was Collected from Four Solar Stills with and without Porous Materials

Source [76]

Salah Abdallah research showed that the uncoated sponge collected the most water during the day, followed by black rocks and coated metallic wiry sponges. On the other hand, the overall average gain in distilled water collected overnight was 28%, 43%, and 60% for coated and untreated metallic wiry sponges and black rocks, respectively. The black rocks boosted the still output by about 17-20%, as illustrated in Figure 9. Adding absorbent materials improved the still's thermal performance by increasing total water collection. The black pebbles absorbed more solar energy than the uncoated and coated metallic wiry sponges [76].

ACTIVE SOLAR STILL

The temperature difference between the water in the basin and the interior glass cover surface is used to determine the passive solar still's production. In passive stills, direct sun radiation is employed to heat the salty water inside the basin. As a result, evaporation occurs, causing a decrease in still production. This is the primary drawback of a passive solar still. As a result, to address the aforementioned issue, several active solar stills are installed to offer additional thermal energy to the still basin. The increased energy consequently boosts the rate of evaporation, increasing yet production even further. Hot water might be supplied into the solar still basin from an external source, such as a solar collector panel. Water might be warmed before being fed into the solar still and then sent to the basin at a continuous low rate [34].

Active Solar Still Enhanced with a Flat Plate Collector

An active solar still comprises of a glass cover, basin, reflector, and pump. The thickness of a glass cover, the length of the flat plate reflector, and the thickness of the basin insulation are all 5 mm, 1 m, and 1.5 mm. The sun's energy heats the brackish water, which is then fed into the still. Sun radiation evaporates water, which collects on the glass cover and flows into the distillate channel. Passive solar stills may cost-effectively produce potable or distilled water [77]. The warmed water from the solar collector was cycled through a tube that linked the basin water or solar still to a flat plate collector. The tube functions as a heat exchanger, transferring heat from the warmed water to the basin water.

Temperature, freshwater productivity, exergy, energy, and economic study has been conducted on the four solar stills. According to the statistics, the solar still's glass temperature ranged from 08.00 to 11.30, which was higher than one of conventional solar still. The solar collector demonstrated the highest average energy and exergy efficiency. The glass covers effectively boosted freshwater output by 28.9%, from 0.81 L/m² to 1.0436 L/m² per day. Furthermore, when compared to other solar stills, the glass cover is the most affordable, costing only 0.193 \$/L/m² [78].

Kerfah and Rabah conducted the experiment in three days from July 24 to 28, 2016, at the UDES location in Bouismail, Algeria, which revealed in the daily cumulative production study, the condensation chamber was a substantial contributor, accounting for 58% of total production. Incorporating a flat plate collector resulted in a 110% increase in daily production over the standard solar still. Incorporating both the flat plate collector and the condensation chamber resulted in an astonishing 176% increase in daily production. Daily production was measured at 5.9 kg/m² for the active with a condensation chamber, 4.5 kg/m² for the active solar still, and 2.1 kg/m² for the basic solar still. According to economic study, the active solar still with condensation chamber produces more freshwater at a lower cost than the active sun still alone [79].

Active Solar Still with Solar Concentrating Systems

Solar energy is the cleanest and cheapest renewable energy source. However, obtaining and using high temperature heat from a source of solar energy is a significant issue in the contemporary day. Solar concentrator collectors have been studied for some years as a method of focusing solar energy for high-temperature applications while also collecting solar energy. Solar concentrators gather and focus light at a single spot. Solar radiation intensity, angle of incidence, and the concentrator's location in relation to the sun and the heated reactor all influence its performance [80,81]. Solar concentrators may be characterized as parabolic trough, dish, or heliostat field concentrators. In Kerman weather conditions, their suggested solar still system produced 55% more pure water during

the summer than in the winter using a fixed parabolic trough collector. During the summer, parabolic trough collector and tracking systems generated around 1.266 L m⁻² day⁻¹, which was 70% higher than in the winter [82].

Khairat Dawood evaluated the performance of a solar still equipped with two solar parabolic concentrator linked in series and operating at varied oil flow rates. The phase change material was introduced under the basin and inside the evacuated tubes. The conventional solar still generated 3.182 L m⁻² day⁻¹. The system produces 4.7, 6.2, 8.8, and 11.1 L m⁻² per day using 1.5, 1.0, and 0.5 L min⁻¹ of oil low rate and 0.5 L min of nano-oil low rate, respectively [83].

SOLAR STILL DESIGNS DISTILLATE PRODUCTION

Solar still designs are different from the initial design to the operation conditions which also influences on the distillate production. The rate at which water evaporates in a solar still is related to the area of exposed water and other external influences such as air flow and solar radiation emerged as the key influencer on the solar desalination system [79]. The designs which are increasing the free surface area of the water in the basin enhances solar still output.

Table 1. Different Solar Still Design, Location, Operation Conditions, Efficiency and Distillate Output

No	References	Design	Location	Operation condition	Distillate output
1	[21]	single slope basin solar still	Djibouti city(E 43°06.681,N11° 32.958)	-S. I: 4.7-7.3 kWh/m ² /day - Base surface area:0.54 m ² .	-Productivity 2490 mL/day -It was found that a low water amount 6L gives the maximum cumulative
2	[43]	A double-effect solar still	India,Kothrud in Pune, (18.516N,73.85 6E)	-The lower basin area is of 324 mm 9 324 mm, -The upper basin has a dimension of 330 mm 9 324 mm. -Insolation Heat transfer coefficient = 2.5 W/m ² -K	-3.2 L/m ²
3	[45]	Simple stepped cascade stills	Kafrelsheikh university, Egypt, (31.07°N)	-Evaporative cooler -Feed water flow rate 10 L/min is 158.89 N/m ² -0.0263 Watt pumping power	-Production:33.55 L/day -Efficiency:49.01%. -1.25 L/day -Without the cooling unity
4	[84]	Double slope still connected to the FPC	Amman Jordan (31.95° N, 35.91° E)	-Square basin: 0.96 m ² , 0.02 m, Water depth, -0.03 m thick insulation, -Glass cover: 4 mm thick - at 45° inclinations, -FPC: 7 parallel tubes	-Productivity 1.5Kg/m ² . d in conventional - Efficiency 22.26% compared to 28.56% In conventional still
5	[85]	Corrugated wick solar still	Kafrelsheikh, Egypt, (31.07°N)		- Distillate yield 4.1 L/m ² . d -Productivity 145.5% - Efficiency 58% - Still yield 180% higher than the conventional still.
6	[86]	Stepped solar still	Kafrelsheikh, Egypt, (31.07°N)	- Mirror reflector material is used	- Yield 6.35 L/m ² . d -Improvement productivity to 75% over the conventional still without reflectors, - Efficiency 56%
7	[87]	Stepped solar still trays	Kafrelsheikh, Egypt, (31.07°N)	- 5 mm tray depth and 100 mm tray width are used	- Yield 7.4 L/m ² . d -Efficiency 108%~59% -The productivity 165% higher than that the conventional still and efficiency is 66%

8	[88]	Active double effect solar still	New Delhi, India	-Type = single basin solar still -Area = 1 mx1 m	An average of 7.5 l/m ² .day of distilled water was obtained in the active mode with water flow arrangement. In the passive and active modes without arrangements for water flow average output was 2.2 and 3.9 l/day.
9	[89]	Solar still with a flat plate solar collector		-Area of 18 m ² . -Solar irradiance of 672 W/m ² -Vacuum and Inner condenser -Surface cooling.	-Productivity 154.14 kg/d -Efficiency 1.36%
10	[90]	Basin still with PTC and Nano fluid	Tehran, Iran (35.72° N, 51.33° E)	-S. I. 800W/m ² -T maximum 50 °C -Working fluids contains (Al ₂ O ₃ , & CuO, TiO ₂)	-Productivity (15.28 kg/h—15.46 kg/h) with nanofluid use -Efficiency (14.9% to 15.2%)
11	[91]	Effect of aluminum balls on the productivity of solar distillate	Algeria	Area:0.25m ² SI:1100	- Modified Solar Still: 5.09 L/m ² .day -Efficiency 31.6 % -Conventional Solar Still:3.71 L/m ² .day -Efficiency 40.1%
12	[92]	Performance enhancement of a solar still distillation unit: A field investigation	Egypt	-Area 1m ² -sponge thicknesses (0 to 40 mm)	-Production 4.9 L/m ² .day -Efficiency 37%

CONCLUSION

The most essential elements to improve the efficiency of distillate production are the following: climate, depth of water in the basin, basin cover slope and its thickness, construction material, water-glass cover temperature difference, and insulation material and its thickness.

In addition, basin water depth enhances evaporation and still productivity. Also, the temperature conditions and the latitude of the testing area could have a vital impact and the basin cover tilt angle should be equivalent to the latitude angle of the location in order to reach a maximum sun radiation.

Furthermore, cooling the water on the glass could reduce heat loss, increasing the still productivity yield. The insulation thickness should be optimal to prevent or reduce heat loss and improve the efficiency of the still. Porous absorber materials demonstrated an increase in still yield. Some modified and advanced designs are illustrated, incorporating advances and modifications to improve efficiency and reduce radiation loss. The solar still designs include the pyramid, triangular, tubular, double basin, hemispherical, and spherical solar stills. The integration of system components, such as coupling with a PVT, PCM, and solar collectors, is effective in improving the system's daily production performance.

RECOMMENDATION

Water desalination using Solar stills is promising technologies because it generates portable water with solar which is green energy and environmental friendly. However, access to clean water remains a challenge in many areas, particularly in remote areas, due to the low productivity of solar stills. To satisfy those in need, we recommend the following for further research to improve the production of solar stills:

Investigate hybrid design systems that combine solar stills with other renewable energy sources, such as wind or biomass, to offer continuous energy input during periods of low sunshine, thus improving overall distillate output.

Future research should focus on the use of innovative materials to improve effectively heat transfer and condensation to enhance solar still distillate production.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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